

Flood Prediction Using Logistic Regression

Neethu Mariya George
Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
neethumariyageorge@mca.ajce.in

Merin Chacko
Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
merinmanoj@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract — Flood is a chief catastrophe in Kerala, which causes big harm to the residing world. Many people lost their lives due to the flash flood. The model built here is to detect floods using a Machine learning method Logistic Regression. It is a type of zeroes and ones, which makes it less complicated to pre-determine whether the calamity is set to arise or not. The better method for use in the future. In the Future Machine Learning will apprise all of the human efforts capabilities to be able to make matters less difficult.

Keywords—flood prediction, Kerala state weather forecasting, logistic regression.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine Learning plays a significant role in each field, it additionally includes studies approximately numerous activities relying on the preceding occasion's associated information. It is the capacity to examine primarily based totally on reviews that are most effective and viable while we've got some original, particular, whole information. Thus, in order to apply ML, we want to take together all of the essential information. The information then required to be pre-processed in order that it may be carried forward for similar operations or functioning. It is important to keep know-how approximately the to-be-had information to apply it in the quality manner feasible. We can use exceptional algorithms to get accuracy primarily based totally on the prevailing information. We have used Logistic Regression to come up with a fine outcome. Floods are the most detrimental herbal catastrophe in this world. On occasion of a heavy flood, it could break an entire community. It is important to increase flood prediction as a mechanism to are expecting and decrease the flood risk. It proves important for alerting residents to take early proceedings such as evacuating fast to a more secure and better place. The dataset from visualcrossing.com contains weather data of the Kottayam district and uses certain features in the dataset used to detect prediction. It certainly defines the once year as nicely because the month-to-month rainfall information which proves this machine's greater accuracy, and it confirms its reliability, efficiency, and assured dependence as properly. This version offers us a nicely described concept of the way the Logistic Regression Algorithms work nicely with particular information. This set of rules solves 1/2 of the case due to its binary-categorized nature. The intention of this specific machine is to make contributions to the improvement of ML as nicely and to improve the situations of Living Life in case of calamity.

II. RELATED WORKS

Many scientists have labored over the years to return back up with powerful techniques to are expecting floods beforehand of time to give Kerala a sufficient lead time.

Shafizadeh-Moghadam et al. [1] have enforced machine learning, statistical models, and ensemble models for assessing flood susceptibility. They recognized 11 factors

that contribute to floods. They use machine learning models such as Artificial neural networks (ANN), Classification and regression trees, Flexible discriminant analysis, generalized linear model.

Han et al. [2] implemented SVM models to locate floods. They experimented with exclusive kernel tricks and various combinations of input. To determine the effectiveness of new models, they as compared them with the Naive, Trend, and Transfer function models. It was observed that SVM anticipated flood with better accuracy in contrast to the TF model.

Khosravi et al. [3] did a comparative take look at the decision trees algorithm to create a flash flood susceptibility model. Logistic model trees, decreased error pruning trees, Naive Bayes Trees, and Alternating Decision Trees had been used for the take a look at. They used the records benefit ratio and multicollinearity diagnostics technique for function selection. After reading the results, it became visible that the ADT version achieved the best.

Chowdhury et al. [4] approached locating the collinearity of Sea-floor temperature in a flood-affected area. They discovered the statistical relationship using principal component analysis. To assemble a model to detect flood, a couple of regression evaluation become done. The statistical version makes use of SST, rainfall, and streamflow in Bangladesh to function as predictors.

Zhaoli Wang et al. [5] Support vector machines are being utilized as a benchmark for risk assessment. Growing the pattern length and the number of classification trees can help reduce the RF's training and testing errors. Their findings imply that they may be able to provide a distinctive and incredibly effective method to evaluate flooding chances.

III. METHOD OF PREDICTION

The dataset is taken through weather data and enterprise evaluation tools referred to as Visual crossing, wherein statistics from various locations have been gathered. In the training phase, the system is trained via means of fitting a model to the dataset's records through the use of the chosen set of rules. In the testing phase, the system is tested, with inputs being fed into it and its functionality being examined. The records applied for training or testing out ought to be suitable as the precision is confirmed. Because the system is designed to predict the flood the appropriate algorithm has to be utilized that is accurate. Logistic Regression is an affect flood prediction: Humidity, Precipitation, and Temperature.

Figure 1: Sample Data

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] H. Shafizadeh-Moghadam, R. Valavi, H. Shahabi, K. Chapi, and A. Shirzadi, "Novel forecasting approaches using a combination of machine learning and statistical models for flood susceptibility mapping," *Journal of environmental management*, vol. 217, pp. 1-11, 2018.
- [2] D. Han, L. Chan, and N. Zhu, "Flood forecasting using support vector machines," *Journal of hydroinformatics*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 267-276, 2007.
- [3] K. Khosravi, B. T. Pham, K. Chapi, A. Shirzadi, H. Shahabi, I. Revhaug, I. Prakash, and D. T. Bui, "A comparative assessment of decision trees algorithms for flash flood susceptibility modeling at Huaraz watershed, northern Iran," *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 627, pp. 744-755, 2018.
- [4] M. R. Chowdhury and M. N. Ward, "Seasonal flooding in Bangladesh variability and predictability," *Hydrological Processes: An International Journal*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 335-347, 2007R.
- [5] ZhaoliWang, ChengguangLai, XiaohongChen, BingYang, ShiweiZhao, XiaoyanBai, "Flood hazard risk assessment model based on random forest", *Journal of Hydrology*: vol.527, August 2015, pp 1130-1141.